

A method to fabricate nanoscale gaps in graphene nano-constrictions by electrical breakdown

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S1. Device fabrication

Figure S1. 3D drawings of the devices fabrication steps. (a) Bare Si/SiO₂ substrate, (b) after graphene transfer, (c) after first PMMA coating, (d) after PMMA development by EBL and subsequent PMMA removal, (e) after graphene etching via reactive ion etching and PMMA stripping, (f) after second PMMA coating, (g) after PMMA development by EBL and subsequent PMMA removal, (h) after metallization, (i) after lift-off. The drawings do not display the outer electrodes observables in the SEM of Figure 1.

The fabrication consists in nine steps. With reference to Figure S1, the chip fabrication steps are described in the following:

- a. *Cleaning of Si/SiO₂ substrates.* First, a Si/SiO₂ substrate is rinsed in water to remove leftover particles from wafer dicing, and then the protective PMMA layer is removed with an ultrasonic bath in acetone for 5 min. Finally, the substrate is rinsed in isopropyl alcohol to remove acetone residues, blown dry with a nitrogen gun, and cleaned in oxygen plasma at 100 W for 5 min to remove organic residues and improve the adhesion of graphene.
- b. *Graphene transfer.* A PMMA-protected graphene sheet on copper substrate is placed on the surface of a Transene copper etchant (CE-100) for 60 min. Once the etching is completed, graphene is transferred with a spoon in sequence to two deionized water baths and a 1:3 solution of HCl 37%: deionized water to remove traces of copper etchant, and finally to a third deionized water bath. From this last water bath, the graphene sheet is transferred on the Si/SiO₂ substrate by fishing, and let dry inside an upside down beaker to avoid surface contamination, with an inclination of 30° - 45°, for 1.5 hours. Afterwards, the Si/SiO₂/graphene sample is annealed first at 80°C for 30 min in air, and then at 80°C in vacuum overnight to remove water residues and increase the adhesion of graphene. The protective PMMA layer on top of graphene is then removed by first placing the samples in acetone for

10 minutes, and then boiling acetone at 54°C for 1 h. The sample is finally rinsed in isopropyl alcohol and blown dried with a nitrogen gun. Step (a) and (b) do not apply to graphene from ANL, as the latter is supplied on a Si/SiO₂ wafer with a PMMA protective layer, neither to graphene from Graphenea, as the latter is supplied on a paper substrate. In the case of graphene from ANL, the wafer is first diced, and then the PMMA removed as described in (b). In the case of graphene from Graphenea, the transfer is done according to the procedure provided by the supplier.

- c. *Preparation of electron beam lithography 1.* As preparation step for the electron beam lithography, the graphene/SiO₂/Si stack is subject to a dehydration bake at 110 °C for 1 min. After that, PMMA 50k (Ar-p 632.06) is spun at 4000 rpm and baked on a hotplate at 180 °C for 5 min. Then a layer of PMMA 950k is spun at 400 rpm for 40 s and baked at 180 °C for 5 min. The double PMMA layer improves the lift-off and the electron beam lithography, as PMMA 50K leaves less residues when removed from graphene instead of from PMMA 950k, and PMMA 950K (Ar-p 672.02) offers higher resolution for the electron beam lithography than PMMA 50k.
- d. *Electron beam lithography 1.* The resist is structured by positive electron beam lithography, developed for 1 min in MiBK:IPA (1:2) and then rinsed for 10 s in IPA. Afterwards it is blown dry with a nitrogen gun.
- e. *Graphene etching.* Graphene is etched via reactive ion etching in an Ar:O₂ plasma (15:30 sccm) at 25 W and 20 mtorr for 30 s. The resist is then removed by immersion in acetone for 20 min.
- f. *Preparation of electron beam lithography 2.* Same as (c), with a spinning speed of 2000 rpm instead of 4000 rpm for the PMMA 50k layer, in order to make a thicker resist layer and facilitate the lift-off procedure.
- g. *Electron beam lithography 2.* Same as (d).
- h. *Electron beam evaporation of metal.* 5 nm of Ti (adhesion layer) and 40 nm of Pt are deposited by electron beam evaporation.
- i. *Lift off.* The microchip is placed in acetone for 60 min to remove the PMMA and lift-off the metal in excess.

In this work, the chips were designed to include about 200 devices each. The number of working devices per chip depended on the graphene coverage: since the transfer of graphene was done by the operator without the auxiliary of a machine, the variability of working devices was quite large from chip to chip.

S2. Graphene growth

Figure S2. Optical images of graphene (white shapes) on copper substrate. The growth was interrupted after a short time to optically isolate graphene crystalline islands. The crystalline islands are separated enough to create grain size larger than 20 μm .

Empa polycrystalline graphene is grown by Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD) in a tube furnace (Three zone HZS, Carbolite) on 25 μm thick copper foils (Foil 2017, No. 46365, Alfa Aesar), according to a procedure designed to give crystalline grains with average size of about 20 μm . The growth includes a thorough cleaning procedure of the copper substrates, followed by the actual growth in the CVD furnace. The cleaning procedure of the copper substrates consists in the following steps: (i) ultrasonic bath in acetone for 15 min, (ii) rinsing in isopropyl alcohol, (iii) immersion in deionized water for 5 min, (iv) etching in acetic acid for 30 min, (v) immersion in deionized water for 5 min, (vi) ultrasonic bath in deionized water for 1 min, and (vii) rinsing in ethanol. The substrates are then blown dry with a nitrogen gun and loaded in the CVD tube furnace. The furnace is first evacuated to base pressure (ca. 10^{-2} mbar), and then the substrates are annealed at 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3 hours in a 200 sccm Ar laminar flow, with a downstream pressure below 1 mbar. Finally, 20 sccm of H_2 is added to the Ar flow, and after 2 min the graphene growth is initiated by the addition of 1.2 sccm of CH_4 at a downstream pressure below 1 mbar. The growth takes 12 min, and is terminated by stopping the flow of CH_4 , opening the lid of the tube furnace, and circulating air with a fan to allow for an abrupt drop in temperature. The resulting graphene on copper substrates is finally covered by a protective layer of PMMA 50K (Allresist AR-P 632.12, 3000 rpm, 40 s), and the backside of the copper foil is cleaned from graphene with RIE.

In order to estimate the average grain size, the growth is interrupted after a short time and the sample annealed to oxidize the copper substrate. This procedure gives enough contrast to optically isolate crystalline graphene islands with a microscope. During the growth, crystalline islands expand and merge into each other, although remaining separated by grain boundaries. Therefore, the average crystalline grain size can be estimated as the average half distance between islands (see Figure S2 for optical images of representative graphene islands).

S3. I-V traces

Figure S3. Electrical breakdown I-V traces (left) and I-V tunneling traces (right) of all 275 devices fabricated in this work.

S4. Graphene mobility and Dirac point data

Figure S4 shows box plots of mobility and Dirac point of devices from group A, B and C. Data were collected on a population subset, in detail 15 devices from group A, 27 devices from group B, and 4 devices from group C. The Dirac point was measured by back-gating the devices and by taking the gate voltage that corresponds to the minimum of conductance. The mobility was estimated as [1]

$$\mu = \frac{L_{ch}g_m}{W_{ch}C_GV_{DS}}$$

where $g_m = \max\left(\frac{dI_D}{dV_{GS}}\right)$ is the maximum transconductance at given voltage bias, and L_{ch} , W_{ch} and C_G are the channel length, channel width and capacitance, respectively, calculated assuming that only the narrow part of the graphene constriction functions as the channel of the field effect transistor. Consequently, the mobility here reported are slightly underestimated. In detail, the mobility were found to be 1298 ± 1508 V/cm² s (group A), 891 ± 583 V/cm² s (group B) and 555 ± 389 V/cm² s (group C). Data are widely spread, with deviations within the same order of magnitude than the average values. This is attributed to unintentional doping and/or defects that arise as consequence of the fabrication procedure, where the operator handles the graphene transfer without the auxiliary of a machine.

Figure S4. Box plot of mobility (left) and Dirac point (right) of devices from group A, B and C.

S5. Stability diagrams at low temperature

Stability diagram at 9 K of two representative devices from group A. The I-V traces at low temperature are clearly gate-independent, while retaining the typical s-shape of tunneling.

Figure S5. Stability diagram at 9 K of two representative devices from group A.

S6. References

- [1] Schwierz, F., 2010. Graphene transistors. *Nature nanotechnology*, 5(7), pp.487-496.